

Campylobacteriosis – the problem with chicken-as-source

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Abstract

Campylobacteriosis is commonly regarded as the most widespread gastrointestinal bacterial infection world-wide. In spite of the focus on chicken meat contamination and major efforts to manage Campylobacter entry into the retail trade, little real evidence exists for success in reducing the disease burden. Further, there are many unexplained patterns within the data that do not support the chicken-meat-as-source hypothesis.

We review the case against chicken-as-source with the objective of moving the discussion forward. Clearly, some success in reducing the campylobacteriosis burden has occurred, but for further success we need to be clear why chicken, an apparently clear and logical source of infectious human pathology, may not in fact be such a clear-cut hypothesis.

“You must look at facts, because they look at you” Churchill 1925.

Introduction

Campylobacteriosis, a significant gastrointestinal disease, has long been associated with poultry food products (Skirrow, 1977). Chicken is commonly regarded as the dominant source for human infection (Adak *et al.*, 2005; Epps *et al.*, 2013; Stern *et al.*, 2003; Wilson & Baker, 2006). There have been numerous studies supporting this view, and many surveys of incidence of *Campylobacter* contamination of chicken meat products available for retail purchase indicate extensive contamination. However, these indicate an opportunity for infection, not a definitive role for poultry products as the vehicle for infection.

Intensive interventions in the poultry supply chain have been claimed to have reduced human campylobacteriosis in Iceland (Stern *et al.*, 2003) and New Zealand (Sears *et al.*, 2011). Both are island nations with only a domestic source of chicken products. In neither country, though, have these interventions brought case rates much below pre-epidemic rates (Baker *et al.*, 2012; Tustin *et al.*, 2011). For New Zealand, it appears that the single sequence type (ST 474) was the dominant cause of the 2006 winter epidemic, in effect a point source outbreak (McTavish *et al.*, 2008; Muellner *et al.*, 2013) associated with chicken production.

In spite of these limited claims for successful reduction in illness, campylobacteriosis remains a major population health concern worldwide. Perhaps it is time to reconsider the chicken/campylobacteriosis link. There are many exceptions in translating the obvious opportunity for infection via poultry products to a definite and population-wide explanation of sporadic campylobacteriosis. Here, we explore the main problems with a chicken-source attribution model.

Cross contamination

Cross contamination during domestic food preparation is considered the main route to infection from retail meat

products (Baker *et al.*, 2006a; Rosenquist *et al.*, 2003). Many simulation trials and domestic kitchen surveys have confirmed this potential (Cogan *et al.*, 1999; De Jong *et al.*, 2008; Luber *et al.*, 2006; Mattick *et al.*, 2003a; Mattick *et al.*, 2003b; Van Asselt *et al.*, 2008).

A review of domestic kitchen hygiene practices eliminated this route as a risk factor for sporadic campylobacteriosis (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2000; Stenberg *et al.*, 2008). The much lower frequency outbreak reports, however, do commonly indicate cross contamination during food preparation in domestic (Ethelberg *et al.*, 2004; Yoda & Uchimura, 2006) and commercial settings (Mazick *et al.*, 2006; Osimani & Clementi, 2016; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2000).

Casual cross contamination, especially in the domestic setting, is poorly predictive for sporadic campylobacteriosis.

Source identification methods

Biotyping of *Campylobacter* isolates provides a means of defining potential sources for case isolates. There are numerous biotyping methodologies commonly used in epidemiological studies, including serotyping and ribotyping, as well as many genotyping systems such as multilocus sequence typing (MLST), restricted fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) and others.

It is common to find significant commonality in these typing studies between those types found in clinical cases and local sources of chicken products. However, there can also be significant overlap between types prevalent in human clinical isolates and isolates from a range of animals other than chicken, as well as other environmental sources (De Haan *et al.*, 2012; Gilpin *et al.*, 2008; Gilpin *et al.*, 2012; Gilpin *et al.*, 2013; Hearnden *et al.*, 2003; Hudson *et al.*, 1999; Nielsen *et al.*, 2000; Piccirillo *et al.*, 2014; Wilson *et al.*, 2008).

In one phylogenetic study, clinical isolates clustered predominantly with non-livestock clades (Champion *et*

al., 2005). Serotyping profiles overlapping with poultry sources can change in prevalence over time (De Haan *et al.*, 2010) and a whole genome study could only link 24% of cases as potentially attributable to chicken sources (Kovanen *et al.*, 2016).

Water sources commonly carry *Campylobacter* species, including similar types found in local clinical isolates (De Haan *et al.*, 2012; Hokajärvi *et al.*, 2013; Sheerin *et al.*, 2014). Water sources commonly indicate a very broad range of *Campylobacter* biotypes, associated with both farmed and wild animals and birds. Bovine and water sources are known to contribute to seasonal illness of rural residents (Lévesque *et al.*, 2013).

A limited range of biotypes in chicken flocks suggests single infections per flock (Damjanova *et al.*, 2011) while at the same time clinical isolates typically provide a very broad range of biotypes, including multiples per patient (Gilpin *et al.*, 2012). Not surprisingly, doubt has been cast on the reliability of current typing methods for source attribution purposes (Llarena *et al.*, 2016).

Antibiotic resistance in *Campylobacter* species is relatively common, but the incidence of resistance to various antibiotics varies by country and isolate source. A recent review indicated no common reporting of increased antibiotic resistance of isolates from animals associated with a similar resistance in human clinical isolates (McCrackin *et al.*, 2016). Antibiotic resistance in human cases appears to be associated with international travel (Ricotta *et al.*, 2014) or internationally sourced chicken products (Skjøt-Rasmussen *et al.*, 2009). Antibiotic resistance analyses suggest that *C. coli* is the common factor between human and chicken isolates, rather than *C. jejuni* (Szczechowska *et al.*, 2017; Zhao *et al.*, 2015). However, *C. coli* generally accounts for less than 10% of *Campylobacter* infections in chickens or humans. More recently, apparently similar antibiotic resistance of chicken and human clinical isolates within the same serotype lost the similarity when comparing at a genetic level (Ohishi *et al.*, 2017). Determination of antibiotic resistances, while currently useful for clinical decisions, are clearly not that useful for source attribution purposes, and specifically linking chicken sources to human clinical cases.

Recent investigations into **Type VI secretion systems**, not universally present in *Campylobacter*, provide another source attribution investigation mechanism. Isolates from chicken products and urban effluents revealed Type VI secretion system genes only in some chicken isolates and none from effluent in Spain (Ugarte-Ruiz *et al.*, 2014). In Pakistan there was commonality across many sources including waste-water, but not from human isolates (Siddiqui *et al.*, 2015), while in Vietnam there was commonality between human and chicken isolates (Harrison *et al.*, 2014). This relatively new type identification may prove useful for some clinical practices, but already demonstrates ambiguity for linking clinical and chicken isolates.

Where alternative sources are considered, there is overlap between clinical and numerous other sources of isolates. However, the strength of the chicken-as-source concept is so strong that many attribution studies

investigate only commonality between local chicken-sourced and clinical isolates – and so promulgate confirmation bias. More detailed and widespread genotyping exercises will provide a far more detailed picture of human cases and other potential sources.

Seasonal and temporal trends

Campylobacteriosis in humans shows a strong seasonal trend, predominantly a summer peak and winter trough. Minor increases associated with holiday events have been suggested too. Similarly, there is a seasonal trend in chickens, both before slaughter and at retail. However, the increased human incidence commonly develops earlier in the summer season than that of chickens. This has been noted across many countries and over many years (Gilpin *et al.*, 2013; Hanninen *et al.*, 2000; Hartnack *et al.*, 2009; Ishihara *et al.*, 2012; Jonsson *et al.*, 2010; Jore *et al.*, 2010; Meldrum *et al.*, 2005; Patrick *et al.*, 2004; Skarp *et al.*, 2016; Williams *et al.*, 2015). Chicken products may well provide a background source resulting in campylobacteriosis, but this widespread disjoint between seasonality of prevalence is far more suggestive of a common source(s) between humans and chickens than a directional chicken to human infection route.

Human susceptibility appears to vary in characteristic age bands. Young children (under 5 years) and young adults (20-29 years) are most commonly represented (Arsenault *et al.*, 2012; Baker *et al.*, 2006b; Brieseman, 1985; Fitzenberger *et al.*, 2010; Laroche & Magras, 2013; Nichols *et al.*, 2012; Schielke *et al.*, 2014), but with differing seasonal profiles across the age bands (Nelson & Harris, 2011). Temporal changes in susceptibility across age groups appears to have occurred in Australia, with reductions in incidence in the young child and adult groups but an increase in the elderly groupings (Moffatt *et al.*, 2017). Seasonality of infection often also varies by geography, even within a single country (Hearnden *et al.*, 2003). It is hard to justify that food handling practices or seasonal eating styles can differentially affect specific age groups.

An interesting aspect of studies of *Campylobacter* seasonality is the realisation that flies are probably a major source of chicken infection/colonisation (Adhikari *et al.*, 2004; Hald *et al.*, 2004; Rosef *et al.*, 1985; Royden *et al.*, 2016; Ruble, 1986). The later summer seasonal peak in chickens coincides well with delay in fly population development until the summer temperature increase. This delay can be explained by a relatively small overwintering adult fly population requiring higher temperatures to feed and breed (Nichols, 2005). Fly screens are a proven means of reducing *Campylobacter* infection in chicken houses (Bahrndorff *et al.*, 2013; Sommer *et al.*, 2013). Flies have also been suggested as a mechanical means of transmitting *Campylobacter* to humans (Evers *et al.*, 2016; Nelson & Harris, 2006; Nichols, 2005), with fly population reduction already demonstrated to result in reduced childhood diarrhoea (Chavasse *et al.*, 1999; Emerson *et al.*, 1999). The short retention period of *Campylobacter* in or on flies, and lack of ability to be cultured within flies, restricts flies to mechanical vectoring within a few hours of their own

acquiring *Campylobacter* (Gill *et al.*, 2016), although under favourable conditions they can travel kilometre distances in a short time (Kjærsgaard *et al.*, 2015). Of potentially further interest in chicken production is that laboratory strains passaged once through chickens become very significantly more infective for other chickens, possibly giving some explanation why early flock infection typically results in whole flock infection (Cawthraw *et al.*, 1996; Chen *et al.*, 2006).

These factors are rather more indicative of a common, probably environmental, source for both chickens and human cases, rather than directional between them.

Travel and medication

Travel has often been regarded as a risk factor for campylobacteriosis, at markedly varying percentages (Kapperud & Aasen, 1992; Norkrans & Svedhem, 1982; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2000; Stern *et al.*, 2003). Even domestic travel increases risk (Zinszer *et al.*, 2010). Obviously eating patterns and habits are different during travel, but a single dominant food source seems an unlikely culprit other than in outbreak cases.

Proton pump inhibitor use has been noted as a risk factor for campylobacteriosis (Bouwknegt *et al.*, 2014; Neal *et al.*, 1996; Tam *et al.*, 2009; Wei *et al.*, 2017). This neither supports nor disproves sporadic infection from a food source, and may better reflect a lower infectious dose required to cause infection.

Discussion

While there is little doubt that chicken food products can be a source for *Campylobacter* infection in humans, particularly evident in outbreaks of cases, considerable doubt must be placed on the assumption that this is the most prevalent source. Since the most dominant campylobacteriosis pattern is sporadic cases, current epidemiological studies, where they include all potential sources for infection, not only do not indicate a single dominant food source, but also clearly indicate a far more widespread range of sources.

There are many reasons to doubt a single, dominant food source. The primary mechanism considered is cross-contamination in domestic kitchens, yet the evidence for this is mixed at best. Various typing source attribution studies simply indicate human isolates derive from a very wide reservoir of sources, but with a broad overlap common to animals and birds such as food, farm, pet and urban wildlife, including water sources likely contaminated by them.

Human cases themselves give doubt for sole dominant sources other than during occasional outbreaks of cases. The stable and widespread patterns of incidence in different human age bands, especially different seasonal profiles within these bands, are not explained by simple, widespread contamination events during domestic food preparation. In particular, there is poor concordance in seasonal incidence in chickens and human cases, human cases increasing before chicken colonisation.

Finer genetic detail is providing considerably better profiling of potential sources, but to date are largely indicating human cases are exposed, and succumb, to a

very wide range of types apparently derived from many animal and associated environmental sources via currently largely cryptic means.

Conclusion

It would seem that the human campylobacteriosis chicken-as-source view remains as ambiguous today as in 2002 (Tam *et al.*, 2002). Food animal sources are one of many sources and should continue to receive attention, including from an animal health perspective. But to consistently reduce the health burden on humans, we need to explore beyond the obvious potential for infection source to actual causes of infection sources.

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